

Legal aspects of HET: UK

[WP3 – Human enhancement]

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Executive summary

This report provides an overview and brief discussion of some of the relevant legal developments and a summary of the relevant legal scholarship in human enhancement technologies (HETs) in the UK. It has two parts. Part I provides a brief discussion of legal developments and an analysis of national legal scholarship. Part II addresses specific legal questions.

Developments

There have been some amendments in the medical devices regulations since 2008. Two relevant developments in relation to the proliferation of cognitive enhancement devices and the availability/use of drugs for cognitive enhancement, are the Psychoactive Substances Act 2016 and the Human Medicines Regulations 2012. The Department of Health review of Cosmetic Interventions (2013)¹ concluded that “Those having cosmetic interventions are often vulnerable. They take their safety as a given and assume regulation is already in place to protect them”,² and recommended implementation of its recommendations to ensure that individuals’ health and safety was “prioritised ahead of commercial interest”.³

We did not find any significant developments on the need to protect the augmented body (including technology on the human body). Developments in HETs have not led to specific amendments in constitutional or human rights and/or legislation bearing on constitutional or human rights. A new bill has been introduced in the House of Lords called the Cosmetic Surgery (Standards) Bill [HL] 2017-19⁴ which aims to make provision to include medical practitioners specialising in cosmetic surgery in the Specialist Register for medical practitioners.

Legal scholarship

Various aspects of HETs are discussed in UK legal scholarship (see section 3.2). These include novel beings (intelligent conscious life forms created by technologies such as AI, synthetic genomics, gene printing, cognitive enhancement, advanced neuroscience), novel neurotechnologies, cyborgs (integrated persons), legal aspects of cognitive enhancement, regulation of cognitive enhancement devices regulation of the body and bodily autonomy, responsibility enhancement, cosmetic surgery regulation, prosthetics and the therapy/enhancement distinction.

Analysis of specific legal issues

There are various relevant terms to take into account in the discussions on HET regulation. These include definitions of ‘medicinal product’, ‘medical device’, ‘active implantable medical device’, ‘non-medicinal products’ etc. Medical treatment is defined as including nursing, psychological intervention

¹ Department of Health, *Review of the Regulation of Cosmetic Interventions, Final report*, April 2013. https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/192028/Review_of_the_Regulation_of_Cosmetic_Interventions.pdf

² Ibid.

³ Department of Health, op. cit., 2013.

⁴ Cosmetic Surgery (Standards) Bill [HL] 2017-19. <https://services.parliament.uk/bills/2017-19/cosmeticsurgerystandards.html>

and specialist mental health habilitation, rehabilitation and care; there is no definition of ‘enhancement’. While ‘therapy’ is defined, we did not find explicit distinctions or clear-cut clarifications of differences between ‘therapeutic’ and ‘non-therapeutic’

A right to bodily integrity⁵ has been considered as “the most important of civil rights”⁶ and as “the first and most important of the interests protected by the law of tort”.⁷ Legal commentators highlight that while the courts place considerable store by the concept of the right to bodily integrity, protected both as a common law right and under the ECHR, there is little guidance on the content or nature of the right. In some cases it seems indistinguishable from a general autonomy right, and it is far from clear what the contours of the right are.⁸

The legality of enhancement procedures is not entirely clear-cut, as there is no blanket or overarching regulation that is applicable given the variant nature of such procedures and under what they might be classed. The nature of enhancement procedures on offer is often unclear, and (especially in private clinics) might vary and change with medical and technological progress, which makes it a challenge for (effective) regulation.

There is a lack of clarity with regard to the limits on non-therapeutic procedures that can be performed is evident in the case of DIY (do it yourself) human enhancement.

The “law relating to decision-making and consent, particularly for patients who lack capacity, varies across the UK, doctors need to understand the law as it applies where they work”.⁹ The standard of informed consent was developed in case law and it continues to develop but the standards and conditions of informed consent vary across the UK. Consent to treatment is the principle that a person must give permission before they receive any type of medical treatment, test or examination. In cases of cosmetic interventions, the responsibility for seeking consent falls on the doctor carrying out the intervention - practitioners have to ensure that a fully ‘informed consent’ procedure is adopted.

The question of whether protection afforded to the augmented or modified body¹⁰ (body with prosthetics) has not been addressed nationally as such.

There is some protection in terms of law that governs medical devices, i.e., all prosthetic and orthotic device manufacturers have to check if their products meet the criteria for a medical device. It could be argued that overall, an augmented or modified body would enjoy protection and guarantees afforded to a human body (e.g., personal injury protection) and may benefit from specific protections afforded to its parts (e.g., patent or copyright protection, protection from illegal interference with wireless

⁵ Defined by David Feldman as “a right to be free from physical interference”. Feldman, D., *Civil Liberties and Human Rights in England and Wales*, Oxford, 2002, p. 241.

⁶ *R. (on the application of Justin West) v The Parole Board* [2002] EWCA Civ 1641; [2003] 1 W.L.R. 705, at [49], per Hale L.J. in her dissenting judgment.

⁷ *Parkinson v St. James NHS Trust* [2001] EWCA 530; [2002] Q.B. 266.

⁸ Herring, Jonathan, and Jesse Wall, “The Nature and Significance of the Right to Bodily Integrity”, *The Cambridge Law Journal*, Vol. 76, Iss. 3, 2017, pp. 566-588, p. 575.

⁹ General Medical Council, “Consent: patients and doctors making decisions together”, 2008. https://www.gmc-uk.org/-/media/documents/consent---english-0617_pdf-48903482.pdf

¹⁰ Since initially we found no data using these search terms, we widened the search using terms ‘synthetic person’ and ‘cyborg’.

communications, product liability protection for prosthesis),¹¹ though this has not been exactly fully tested in the courts

There is no legislation dealing with the ownership of, for example, of implanted medical devices. There might be one or many claims to ownership in relation to the augmented, modified or synthetic body, i.e., the augmented human, the manufacturer of the augmentation, body part or device; the supplier of the augmentation, body part or device (e.g., a hospital). On implantation, an implant becomes the property of the person in whom it has been implanted and it remains his or her property even if it is subsequently removed. Following the patient's death, it forms part of his or her estate unless there is any specific provision to the contrary. This position is, however, disputed.¹²

Legal issues

The research identified several legal issues related to HETs in the UK (from various perspectives such as: changing human capacities and legal responsibilities, human rights considerations related to informed consent (and the conditions of consent), personal autonomy, privacy¹³, bodily integrity, reproductive rights; legal obligations to take cognitive enhancing drugs; liabilities for failures to enhance; security, safety and product liability and intellectual property rights.

Key challenges

Key challenges include the creation by the law of “artificial constructs that become the object of regulatory attention of dedicated regulators who operate within legally defined spheres of influence or “silos”¹⁴; the law taking ‘bounded object’ approach, constructing medical devices as different types of objects: ‘risk objects’, ‘marketised objects’, ‘innovation objects’;¹⁵ the challenge of promoting safe use’;¹⁶ the destabilisation of the human body and the concept of bodily integrity.¹⁷

Gaps

Gaps identified by this research include:

¹¹ Barfield, Woodrow, and Alexander Williams, "Law, Cyborgs, and Technologically Enhanced Brains", *Philosophies* 2.1, 2017, p.6.

¹² Arguing that “there is no logical contractual way that ownership can pass merely because an item remains in a person's possession”. See Fifield, Kerry, “Ownership of medical implants”, Clarke Wilmott, 2012. <https://www.clarkewillmott.com/blog/ownership-of-medical-implants/>

¹³ Note, “Medical devices can be interpreted to include medical informatics which are impacted by the EU GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation).” British Medical Association, ‘Brexit Briefing Medicines and medical devices regulation Maintaining an effective working relationship between the UK and the EU’ 2017. <https://www.bma.org.uk/-/media/files/pdfs/collective%20voice/influence/europe/bma-brexit-briefing-medicines-and-medical-devices-regulation.pdf?la=en>

¹⁴ Citing Laurie, Graeme, “Liminality and the Limits of Law in Health Research Regulation: What are we Missing in the Spaces in-Between?”, *Medical Law Review*, Volume 25, Issue 1, 2017, pp. 47–72.

¹⁵ Quigley and Ayihongbe, op. cit., 2018.

¹⁶ Maslen, Hannah, et al. “The regulation of cognitive enhancement devices: refining Maslen et al.'s model”, *Journal of Law and the Biosciences*, 2, 3, 2015, pp. 754-767

¹⁷ Wicks, Elizabeth, *The State and the Body: Legal Regulation of Bodily Autonomy*, Hart Publishing, 2016, p.1.

- Legal discussion on reversibility or irreversibility of human enhancement and its consequences.
- How the current and future interests of individuals might be balanced in terms of their enhancement choices and decisions
- “Relatively little attention” in courts to the concept of bodily integrity¹⁸ and preparedness of the courts to deal with the challenges raised by the “the linking of the organic, biological person with synthetic, inorganic parts and devices”.¹⁹
- How the law might address and deal with the replacement of a healthy body part for a prosthetic one – we found no explicit statement of law or academic discourse that shows this is prohibited. However, if such replacement was contrary to the provisions of law, it would be illegal, e.g., is an assault offence, or is carried out in prohibited circumstances (e.g., on an underage person without valid consent) and causes of legal action might arise in cases of clinical/medical negligence.

¹⁸ Herring, Jonathan, and Jesse Wall, “The Nature and Significance of the Right to Bodily Integrity”, *The Cambridge Law Journal*, Vol. 76, Iss. 3, 2017, pp. 566-588 [p. 569]

¹⁹ Quigley and Ayihongbe, op. cit., 2018.

List of tables

- **Table 1:** List of acronyms/abbreviations
- **Table 2:** Glossary of terms

List of acronyms/abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
ASA	Advertising Standards Authority
CAMs	Complementary and alternative medicines
CED	Cognitive enhancement device
EC	European Commission
GMC	General Medical Council
HE	Human Enhancement
HETs	Human Enhancement Technologies
MHRA	Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency
NHS	National Health Service
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence
PIP	Poly Implant Prothèse
tDCS	transcranial direct current stimulation devices
UK	United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland

Table 1: List of acronyms/abbreviations

Glossary of terms

Term	Explanation
Cosmetic interventions	Any intervention, procedure or treatment carried out with the primary objective of changing an aspect of a patient’s physical appearance. This includes surgical and non-surgical procedures, both invasive and non-invasive. <i>GMC Guidance on Cosmetic Interventions</i> .
Human enhancement	A “modification aimed at improving human performance and brought about by science-based and/or technology-based interventions in or on the human body”. SIENNA, <i>Deliverable 3.1 State of the art review</i> , 2018.
Medicinal product	Any substance or combination of substances presented as having properties of preventing or treating disease in human beings; or (b) any substance or combination of substances that may be used by or administered to human beings with a view to (i) restoring, correcting or modifying a physiological function by exerting a pharmacological, immunological or metabolic action, or (ii) making a medical diagnosis. <i>Human Medicines Regulations 2012</i>
Medical device	As defined in the Medical Devices Regulations 2002.
Therapy	Prevention and treatment or cure of disease. <i>Manual of Patent Practice</i> .

Table 2: Glossary of terms

1. Introduction

This report provides an overview and brief discussion of some of the relevant legal developments and a summary of relevant legal scholarship in human enhancement technologies (HETs) in the UK²⁰. Unless specified otherwise, the time period we covered was 2008 to 2018 (though some relevant prior developments are mentioned).

The method used to prepare this report was desktop research. The desk research used methods described in the SIENNA Handbook, primarily the doctrinal and functional methods of legal analysis. We looked at legislation, legislative guidance documents, and legal academic discourse (focussing on the UK) in preparing this report.

2. Scope and limitations of the report

This report has two parts - Part I provides a brief discussion of legal developments and an analysis of national legal scholarship. Part II addresses specific legal questions.

As ‘human enhancement technologies’ or HETs is not a pre-defined field in the UK and might touch upon many and disparate legal areas, one of the key challenges was finding information using the keywords or search terms (i.e., human enhancement, non-therapeutic human enhancement, human enhancement technologies, non-therapeutic services, non-therapeutic medical services, non-medical health devices, lifestyle medical services) though these were very useful at the same time to maintain focus. To address this and where relevant, we expanded our search terms where needed to successfully answer individual questions. We used additional terms such as augmented body, modified body, cyborg, synthetic body/integrated person, cognitive liberty, prosthetic implants+ law/regulation +UK to make sure we captured essential information. We do recognise, however, that our results may not present exhaustive or definitive answers to the questions posed.

3. Part I: Summary of legal developments and an analysis of national legal scholarship

This part summarises legal developments during the last five to 10 years, following the steps outlined and discussed in SIENNA Task 3.2. The research sources used included: the British and Irish Legal

²⁰ The United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland (UK) is made up of four countries, i.e., England, Wales, Scotland and Northern Ireland. Some law in the UK is applicable throughout, other laws are more country-specific. There are three legal systems in operation – one each for England and Wales (common law), Scotland (mixed) and Northern Ireland. The main sources of law are: acts of parliament, case law (common law is an important source of key legal principles, particularly in relation to the preservation of the rights of the individual against the state and the rule of law) and European Union law. The UK is subject to international legal obligations and is a signatory to numerous international treaties and conventions, notably the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR).

Information Institute²¹, Legislation.gov.uk²², and the websites of the relevant regulatory authorities. Search terms included enhancement, cognitive enhancement (devices), new laws, new regulations, cognitive enhancement drugs, CRISPR-Cas, and augmented/modified body.

3.1. Legal developments

This section first covers developments relating to national level legislation relevant to HETs. Next it looks at whether developments of HETs have led to amendments in constitutional or human rights and/or legislation bearing on constitutional or human rights in the UK.

- 3.1.1. Have there been attempts or plans to adopt at national level new legislation or set up new regulatory bodies in response to new development and/or increased use of human enhancement technologies²³? Have there been/are there attempts to regulate²⁴ how HETs are designed, set up, commissioned or used?

There have been some amendments in the medical devices regulations since 2008.²⁵

With regard to the proliferation of cognitive enhancement devices and the availability/use of drugs for cognitive enhancement, two relevant developments include:

- The **Psychoactive Substances Act 2016** creates a blanket ban on the production, distribution, sale and supply of psychoactive substances²⁶ in the United Kingdom. It makes it an offence to produce, supply, offer to supply, possess with intent to supply, import, export, or possess in a custodial institution, psychoactive substances and provides for civil sanctions²⁷ to enable the police and local authorities to adopt a graded response to the production, supply etc of psychoactive substances in appropriate cases.

²¹ <http://www.bailii.org/>

²² <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/>

²³ New developments and/or increased use of human enhancement technologies as outlined in the SIENNA D3.1 State-of-the-art Review. Examples of areas of interest specified by task leader include: the proliferation of cognitive enhancement devices and their easy availability; the use of drugs for cognitive enhancement (including administration of the drugs to children); recent development of CRISPR-Cas systems; the need to protect the augmented body (including technology ON the human body). SIENNA was also interested in developments concerning the more common and established (“traditional”) types of enhancement (e.g. the issues of age limit in cosmetic surgery or the problem of doping) as long as they fit the definition of HET.

²⁴ This could be both to restrict or advance the development or use of such applications.

²⁵ I.e., the Medical Devices (Fees Amendment) Regulations 2017; The Medical Devices (Amendment) Regulations 2013, The Medical Devices (Fees Amendment) Regulations 2013, The Medical Devices (Amendment) Regulations 2012, The Medical Devices (Fees Amendment) Regulations 2010, The Medical Devices (Fees Amendments) Regulations 2009, and The Medical Devices (Amendment) Regulations 2008

²⁶ Defined as “as any substance which is capable of producing a psychoactive effect in a person who consumes it and is not an exempted substance”. Exempted substances include: Exempted substances are alcohol, tobacco, medicines and controlled drugs, caffeine and foodstuffs such as nutmeg and chocolate.

²⁷ I.e., prohibition notices, premises notices, prohibition orders and premises orders (breach of the two orders will be a criminal offence).

- **The Human Medicines Regulations 2012** implementing the European Directive 2001/83/EC relating to medicinal products for human use, consolidates and replaces most of the Medicines Act 1968 and other regulations governing the control, manufacture and supply of human medicines.

With regard to recent development of CRISPR-Cas systems, the Human Tissue Authority (created by the Human Tissue Act 2004) oversees the editing of somatic cells in research and clinical contexts and regulates somatic therapies (licenced by the MRHA). The Human Tissues Act 2004 deals with the removal, storage and use of human organs and other tissue for scheduled purposes. The Human Fertilisation and Embryology Authority (HFEA) regulates the editing of human eggs and sperm (known as germ cells) in a research context. Domestic law currently does not permit editing of germ cells or embryos in a clinical context.²⁸

With regard to developments concerning the more common and established (“traditional”) types of enhancement, the Poly Implant Prothèse (PIP) Implant²⁹ scandal (PIP breast implants were withdrawn in the UK in 2010³⁰), the Department of Health in 2013 reviewed the regulation of Cosmetic Interventions³¹ and concluded that, “Those having cosmetic interventions are often vulnerable. They take their safety as a given and assume regulation is already in place to protect them.”³² The Review suggested implementation of its recommendations to ensure that individuals’ health and safety was “prioritised ahead of commercial interest”.³³

The Guardian reports³⁴ that it along with other organisations including the BBC, Le Monde and Süddeutsche Zeitung, coordinated by the International Consortium of Investigative Journalists (ICIJ), has uncovered stories of faulty pacemakers, spinal implants that disintegrated and breast implants linked to a rare form of cancer. The investigation outlines that “in the UK alone, regulators received 62,000 “adverse incident” reports linked to medical devices between 2015 and 2018. A third

²⁸ Noting here, that the Nuffield Council on Bioethics report on “[Genome editing and human reproduction: social and ethical issues](#)” published in July 2018 concluded “that the use of heritable genome editing interventions to influence the characteristics of future generations could be ethically acceptable in some circumstances, provided: it is intended to secure, and is consistent with, the welfare of a person who may be born as a consequence of interventions using genome edited cells; and it upholds principles of social justice and solidarity, i.e. it should not be expected to increase disadvantage, discrimination, or division in society.” Even though the report’s conclusions are conditional, this has been seen by some as an approval of sorts for “designer babies” (and generated discussion on this) and even “a red carpet for unrestricted use of inheritable genetic engineering, and a gilded age in which some are treated as genetic ‘haves’ and the rest of us as ‘have-nots’”. See Knapton, Sarah, “Designer babies on horizon as ethics council gives green light to genetically edited embryos”, *The Telegraph*, 17 July 2018. <https://www.telegraph.co.uk/science/2018/07/16/designer-babies-horizon-ethics-council-gives-green-light-genetically/>

²⁹ Poly Implant Prothèse (PIP) are silicone breast implants containing unapproved silicone gel.

³⁰ National Health Service, “PIP breast implants”, 2016. <https://www.nhs.uk/conditions/pip-implants/>

³¹ Department of Health, *Review of the Regulation of Cosmetic Interventions, Final report*, April 2013. https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/192028/Review_of_the_Regulation_of_Cosmetic_Interventions.pdf

³² Ibid.

³³ Department of Health, op. cit., 2013.

³⁴ Osborne, Hilary, Hannah Devlin and Caelainn Barr, “Revealed: faulty medical implants harm patients around world”, 25 Nov 2018. <https://www.theguardian.com/society/2018/nov/25/revealed-faulty-medical-implants-harm-patients-around-world>

of the incidents had serious repercussions for the patient, and 1,004 resulted in death”.³⁵ The Guardian also quotes the Chair of the government’s safety review of medical devices as saying that “patients cannot rely on existing regulations to protect them from dangerous products that could lead to pain and physical harm”.³⁶

We did not find any significant developments on the need to protect the augmented body (including technology on the human body).

3.1.2. Developments in HETs that have led to amendments in constitutional or human rights and/or legislation bearing on constitutional or human rights

This section looks at whether developments of HETs have led to amendments in constitutional or human rights and/or legislation bearing on constitutional or human rights.

The UK’s constitutional laws and rules are not codified in a single, written document. Human rights law is enshrined in the Human Rights Act 1998. The UK hasn’t signed the Council of Europe Convention for the protection of Human Rights and Dignity of the Human Being with regard to the Application of Biology and Medicine: Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine ETS No.164. (i.e., Oviedo Convention) which is one of the most important legal documents in the field and could have an impact on national policies.

Developments in HETs have not led to specific or direct amendments in this respect.

Some cases relating to the right to bodily integrity are covered in Section 4.3.1.

One development worth mentioning was the Cosmetic Surgery (Standards of Practice) Bill 2016-17³⁷ which was introduced to make provisions for the training, qualifications and certification of medical practitioners conducting cosmetic surgical procedures; to establish a code of practice for the provision of information to patients on the options and risks in relation to such procedures; to make provision about permissible treatments and the advertising of such treatments; and for connected purposes. The Bill was expected to have its second reading debate on 12 May 2017; however, as a General Election was called and Parliament dissolved from 3 May 2017, the Bill fell and no further action was taken. A new bill has been introduced in the House of Lords called the Cosmetic Surgery (Standards) Bill [HL] 2017-19³⁸ which aims to make provision to include medical practitioners specialising in cosmetic surgery in the Specialist Register for medical practitioners. Its first reading was held on 12 July 2017 (second reading yet to be scheduled).

³⁵ Ibid.

³⁶ Devlin, Hannah and Hilary Osborne, “Safety regulations for medical implants condemned by review chair”, *The Guardian*, 26 Nov 2018. <https://www.theguardian.com/society/2018/nov/26/implant-files-safety-review-chair-regulations-not-fit-for-use>

³⁷ Cosmetic Surgery (Standards of Practice) Bill 2016-17. <https://services.parliament.uk/bills/2016-17/cosmeticsurgerystandardspractice.html>

³⁸ Cosmetic Surgery (Standards) Bill [HL] 2017-19. <https://services.parliament.uk/bills/2017-19/cosmeticsurgerystandards.html>

3.2. Legal scholarship

This section assesses through a literature search academic articles that have appeared in the past 10 years that address legal aspects of human enhancement. The search was restricted to academic journal articles, books and book chapters written in the national language (English) with a strong focus on legal issues as evident from the UK perspective.

Various aspects of HETs are discussed in UK legal scholarship³⁹ – these include novel beings⁴⁰ (intelligent conscious life forms created by technologies such as AI, synthetic genomics, gene printing, cognitive enhancement, advanced neuroscience), novel neurotechnologies⁴¹, cyborgs (integrated persons)⁴², legal aspects of cognitive enhancement⁴³, regulation of cognitive enhancement devices⁴⁴, regulation of the body⁴⁵ and bodily autonomy⁴⁶, responsibility enhancement⁴⁷, cosmetic surgery regulation⁴⁸, prosthetics and the therapy/enhancement distinction⁴⁹.

³⁹ Search terms used included 'UK' and one of the following terms: human enhancement, non-therapeutic human enhancement, (human) enhancement technologies, non-therapeutic services, non-therapeutic medical services, non-medical health devices, lifestyle medical services. We searched on the website of the Medical Law Review, Journal of Law and the Biosciences and used Google scholar to supplement this. This was not an exhaustive search and limited to the time period 2008-2018. We also excluded scholarship that was general and did not focus specifically on UK law.

⁴⁰ Lawrence, David R., and Margaret Brazier, "Legally Human? 'Novel Beings' and English Law", *Medical law review* 26.2, 2018, pp. 309-32.

⁴¹ Nuffield Council on Bioethics, *Novel neurotechnologies: intervening in the brain*, June 2013.

http://nuffieldbioethics.org/wp-content/uploads/2013/06/Novel_neurotechnologies_report_PDF_web_0.pdf.

This discusses regulation. It specifies that the development and clinical use of these technologies falls into two distinct areas of regulation: The devices used in transcranial brain stimulation (TBS), deep brain stimulation (DBS), brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) for medical purposes are regulated as medical devices, and can be marketed once they carry a 'CE mark' to indicate compliance with European law. Neural stem cell therapies are regulated as advanced therapeutic medicinal products (ATMPs) – more closely resembling the regulation of pharmaceuticals.

⁴² Quigley, Muireann, and Semande Ayihongbe, "Everyday Cyborgs: On Integrated Persons and Integrated Goods", *Medical law Review*, Vol. 26, Iss. 2, 2018, pp. 276-30.

⁴³ Goold, I., "The Legal Aspects of Cognitive Enhancement", in Ruud ter Meulen, Ahmed D Mohamed, and Wayne Hall (eds), *Rethinking Cognitive Enhancement: A Critical Appraisal of the Neuroscience and Ethics of Cognitive Enhancement*, OUP, 2017, pp. 250-273.

⁴⁴ Maslen, Hannah, et al. "The regulation of cognitive enhancement devices: refining Maslen et al.'s model", *Journal of Law and the Biosciences*, 2, 3, 2015, pp. 754-767; Maslen, H., Douglas, T., Kadosh, R. C., Levy, N., & Savulescu, J., "The regulation of cognitive enhancement devices: extending the medical model", *Journal of Law and the Biosciences*, 1(1), 2014, pp. 68-93; Maslen, H., Savulescu, J., Douglas, T., Levy, N., & Cohen Kadosh, R. (2013). 'Regulation of devices for cognitive enhancement', *The Lancet*, 382(9896), pp. 938-939.

⁴⁵ Latham, Melanie, "The Legal, Medical and Cultural Regulation of the Body", *Medical Law Review*, Volume 19, Issue 3, 1 September 2011, pp. 492-495.

⁴⁶ Wicks, Elizabeth, *The State and the Body: Legal Regulation of Bodily Autonomy*, Bloomsbury Publishing, 2016.

⁴⁷ Goold, I., & Maslen, H., "Responsibility Enhancement and the Law of Negligence", in Jens Clausen and Neil Levy (eds.), *Handbook of Neuroethics*, 2015, pp. 1363-1380.

⁴⁸ Latham, Melanie, "If It Ain't Broke, Don't Fix It?": Scandals, 'Risk', And Cosmetic Surgery Regulation in the UK and France", *Medical Law Review*, Volume 22, Issue 3, 1 September 2014, pp. 384-408.

⁴⁹ Karpin, Isabel, and Roxanne Mykitiuk, "Going out on a limb: prosthetics, normalcy and disputing the therapy/enhancement distinction", *Medical Law Review*, Vol. 16, Iss. 3, 1 October 2008, pp. 413-436. The article,

Lawrence and Brazier have analysed “novel beings—intelligent, conscious life-forms sapient in the same way or greater than are human beings”.⁵⁰ They examine this using the concept of the ‘reasonable creature in being’ in English law, the right to life as founded in the European Convention on Human Rights and the attempts to endow human status on animals in recent years. Lawrence and Brazier conclude “that there is a strong case to recognize such ‘novel’ beings as entitled to the same fundamental rights to life, freedom from inhumane treatment, and liberty as we are”.⁵¹

Quigley and Ayihongbe suggest, “Law must re-orientate itself; it must meet the needs of the assemblage of integrated persons and integrated goods. Unless the law evolves, it is going to struggle to adequately and justifiably deal with the challenges wrought by advancing technology generally, and those of the assemblage of integrated persons and integrated good in particular. Exactly what the shape of the law should be in this respect remains to be explored and debated”.⁵² Their analysis identifies and examines legal issues in five areas: (i) medical device regulation, safety and product liability (ii) damage to devices and liability (iii) data and privacy (iv) security and biohacking and (v) intellectual property rights.

Goold examines a range of legal issues arising from the emergence of putative cognitive enhancement technologies (focussing on pharmaceuticals such as modafinil and transcranial direct current stimulation (tDCS) devices, a broad range of areas of law. Goold examines product liability⁵³, contract law (concluding that “in the future we may well see cases where purchasers bring claims when a purported enhancer does not do as promised”⁵⁴), negligence⁵⁵, criminal law (where Goold sees enhancers raising issues depending on what drugs and devices are developed, e.g., use to bring defendant up to capacity to stand trial, or as part of reintegrative shaming approaches⁵⁶ or their role in enabling people to give competent consent when they might otherwise be incapable of doing so⁵⁷). Goold also looks at human rights law and highlights “we might also see the emergence of new human rights in response to our changed capacities, or at least our ability to change those capacities that may come with the emergence of enhancement technologies” and “that human rights principles already

inter alia, discusses the legislative attempts to regulate the uses of preimplantation genetic diagnosis (PGD) in the UK.

⁵⁰ Lawrence, David R., and Margaret Brazier, “Legally Human? ‘Novel Beings’ and English Law”, *Medical law review* 26.2, 2018, pp. 309-32.

⁵¹ Lawrence, David R., and Margaret Brazier, “Legally Human? ‘Novel Beings’ and English Law”, *Medical law review*, 26.2, 2018, pp. 309-32.

⁵² Quigley and Ayihongbe, op. cit., 2018.

⁵³ Goold op.cit., 2017, p. 255. Goold states, “The current structure for managing products that might cause harm can encompass cognitive-enhancing drugs and devices. The implications of this coverage is that producers are protected against unknowable risks that their products might carry. The consumer will bear these. Given the concerns identified in this section, there is clearly work that needs to be done to improve our current regulatory approach to ensure that users are not left unprotected from harm. We ought also to think in terms of devising regulatory approaches that prevent harms rather than merely compensate consumers after the fact.”

⁵⁴ Goold op.cit., 2017, p. 256

⁵⁵ Here Goold concludes that “a pure failure to enhance is unlikely to lead to liability. That said, there might be contexts in which someone assumes responsibility in such a way that an obligation to enhance does arise.” Goold op.cit., 2017, p. 257

⁵⁶ Goold, op.cit., 2017, p. 259.

⁵⁷ Goold, op.cit., 2017, p. 260.

have a role to play in how we address issues raised by cognitive enhancement. This role is likely to be increasingly important as our capacity to enhance improves⁵⁸. Goold also examines issues pertaining to children⁵⁹, employment and discrimination law⁶⁰, and obligations to enhance.

Goold underscores that “Regulatory approaches to enhancement will also be complicated by the difficulties associated with determining what actually constitutes enhancement and if we use enhancement as the focal point of our regulation, we may hit hurdles or create unnecessary problems.⁶¹ Goold concludes:

We must, on the one hand, be mindful to avoid creating new schemes of regulation focused solely on cognitive enhancement, as these may become outdated as the science improves. We must also ensure that any legal developments are grounded firmly in what is technologically possible or likely to be possible.⁶²

Wicks questions the limits of the legitimate role of the state in regulating the human body and makes practical recommendations to enhance and support bodily autonomy.⁶³ Wicks underlines how “English law has developed to protect a liberal, individualised form of autonomy” especially within realm of medical law⁶⁴ (see 1992 case in *Re T*⁶⁵). Wicks further underlines how English law not only respects reasonable choices (citing the *Bland* case⁶⁶) and highlights, “there seems little interest in greater state intervention to restrict autonomous choices about changing the body by means of cosmetic surgery.”⁶⁷

In their analysis of cognitive enhancers, Goold and Maslen⁶⁸, using a scenario involving a tired surgeon, examine the question: When, if at all, might someone be legally obliged to take a cognitive-enhancing drug? Making the case that the “law must be sure that responsibility has been placed on the right shoulders”, they conclude that “at the current time, English law is unlikely to find a surgeon who takes, or fails to take, an enhancer liable in negligence”.⁶⁹

⁵⁸ Goold, op.cit., 2017, p. 261.

⁵⁹ Goold suggests it is “unlikely that a court would enforce an enhancement on a child over the parent’s refusal”. Goold, op.cit., 2017, p. 262.

⁶⁰ Issues raised include issues of safe working practices and pressures (or obligations) to enhance, selection of employees and discrimination. Goold, op.cit., 2017, p. 262.

⁶¹ Goold, op.cit., 2017, p. 269.

⁶² Goold, op.cit., 2017, p. 270.

⁶³ Wicks, op. cit., 2016.

⁶⁴ Wicks, op. cit., 2016, p. 4.

⁶⁵ *Re T (adult: refusal of medical treatment)* [1992] 4 All ER 649 .

⁶⁶ *Airedale N.H.S. Trust v Bland* [1993] A.C. 789 [HL].

⁶⁷ Wicks, op. cit., 2016, p. 113.

⁶⁸ Goold, I., & Maslen, H., “Responsibility Enhancement and the Law of Negligence”, in Jens Clausen and Neil Levy (eds.), *Handbook of Neuroethics*, 2015, pp. 1363-1380.

⁶⁹ Goold, & Maslen, op. cit., 2015, p. 1378.

Maslen et al's 2014 model⁷⁰ for regulating CEDs was revised in 2015⁷¹. The revised version examines theoretical points pertaining to the definition of a CED and the distinction between treatment and enhancement and addresses challenges raised by the prospect of implementing their regulatory framework. It also addresses some wider societal considerations relating to users and other stakeholders and revisits the broader regulatory context within which the various discussions are situated.

Latham⁷² looks at current proposals for legislation in the UK following the PIP silicone implant scandal as an example of the risk-regulation premise and argues that the UK and France have both reacted to healthcare scandals and the ensuing societal conception of risk by drawing up more thorough legislation on cosmetic surgery than previously existed. The article compares the French 2002 Kouchner law and UK 2013 Keogh Report⁷³ to establish whether the UK can learn from the French legislation when it comes to drafting actual regulation in the future. It also presents arguments whether risk aversion may make better law.

Karpin and Mykitiuk⁷⁴ examine how therapy and enhancement are characteristically understood in ethical, medical and legal contexts, and how these understandings rely on unstated assumptions about the meanings attributed to different forms of embodiment: normal and disabled, healthy and diseased, able-bodied and impaired, and beautiful and functional. They suggest the therapy-enhancement distinction is inadequate and unhelpful to guide ethical analysis and medical and regulatory decision-making and cannot adequately assist us in adjudicating when it is appropriate to allow individual choice and autonomy to govern the use of these technologies and when the State should intervene.

4. Part II: Analysis of specific legal issues

This part analyses specific legal issues of HETs identified by SIENNA.

4.1. Background information

⁷⁰ Maslen, H., T., Douglas, R. C. Kadosh, N. Levy, J. & Savulescu, "The regulation of cognitive enhancement devices: extending the medical model", *Journal of Law and the Biosciences*, 1(1), 2014, pp. 68-93. This argued that the sale of cognitive enhancement devices (CEDs)—such as transcranial direct current stimulators (tDCS) and transcranial magnetic stimulators (TMS)—should be regulated under medical devices legislation (for instance, the Medical Devices Directive (MDD) within the European Union).

⁷¹ Maslen, H., T., Douglas, R. C. Kadosh, N. Levy, J. & Savulescu, "The regulation of cognitive enhancement devices: refining Maslen et al.'s model", *Journal of Law and the Biosciences*, 2, 3, 2015, pp. 754-767.

⁷² Latham, Melanie, "If It Ain't Broke, Don't Fix It?": Scandals, 'Risk', And Cosmetic Surgery Regulation in the UK and France", *Medical Law Review*, Volume 22, Issue 3, 1 September 2014, pp. 384–408.

⁷³ Department of Health, Review of the Regulation of Cosmetic Interventions, April 2013. https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/192028/Review_of_the_Regulation_of_Cosmetic_Interventions.pdf

⁷⁴ Karpin, Isabel, Roxanne Mykitiuk, "Going out on a limb: prosthetics, normalcy and disputing the therapy/enhancement distinction", *Medical Law Review*, Vol. 16, Iss. 3, 1 October 2008, pp. 413–436.

The major medical laws in the UK include statutes and statutory instruments⁷⁵. Relevant applicable statutes include the Access to Medical Treatments (Innovation Act) 2016, Care Act 2014, Consumer Protection Act 1987, Consumer Rights Act 2015, Health and Social Care Act 2012, Human Fertilisation and Embryology Act 1990, Human Rights Act 1998 (which gives further effect to rights and freedoms guaranteed under the European Convention on Human Rights), the Human Tissue Act 2004, the Mental Capacity Act 2005, the Mental Health Act 2007, National Health Service Act 2006, NHS Redress Act 2006, Offences Against the Person Act 1861, Public Health (Control of Disease) Act 1984, the Data Protection Act 2018. Some statutes might apply only to specific jurisdictions (i.e., Scotland or Wales). In addition to the statutes and statutory instruments, there are practice directions, department of Health and regulatory agency guidance, guidance from the General Medical Council, other Codes of practice and applicable policy guidance.

Some UK legislation implements EU legislation (e.g., the Human Medicines Regulations 2012 implement into UK law EU legislation such as Directive 2001/83/EC on the Community code relating to medicinal products for human use (Community Code). The UK Medical Devices Regulations 2002 implemented the three EU medical device directives⁷⁶ into national law. We also note the adoption of Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices, amending Directive 2001/83/EC, Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 and repealing Council Directives 90/385/EEC and 93/42/EEC and Regulation (EU) 2017/746 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on in vitro diagnostic medical devices and repealing Directive 98/79/EC and Commission Decision 2010/227/EU. Both these entered into force on 25 May 2017. The Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency (MHRA) regulates medicines, medical devices and blood components for transfusion in the UK.⁷⁷

4.2. Terminology and legal demarcations

4.2.1. Does the domestic law in your country provide a legal definition of “health” or the state of “health”? If yes, please quote the relevant source. Has the question of the definition of “health” been addressed in the case law?

Our search of health-related legislation showed domestic law does not provide a definition of ‘health’. There is legislation such as Public Health (Control of Disease) Act 1984 and the Health and Social Care

⁷⁵ E.g., [Medicines \(Traditional Herbal Medicinal Products for Human Use\) Regulations](#) 2005, Medicines for Human Use (Clinical Trials) Regulations 2004, The National Health Service (Pharmaceutical Services) Regulations 1992.

⁷⁶ Directive 93/42/EEC concerning medical devices (Medical Devices Directive), Directive 90/385/EEC on active implantable medical devices (Active Implantable Medical Devices Directive) and the Directive 98/79/EC on in vitro diagnostic medical devices (IVD Directive).

⁷⁷ <https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/medicines-and-healthcare-products-regulatory-agency/about>

Act 2012⁷⁸ that governs public health and social care. The Health and Social Care Act 2012⁷⁹ contains legal duties about health inequalities. The contexts of health mentioned in that Act include: physical and mental health and the prevention, diagnosis and treatment of physical and mental illness.⁸⁰ However, there are policy statements on public health. For example, public health is viewed as “helping people to stay healthy, and protecting them from threats to their health”,⁸¹ or “very broadly as a resource for everyday life which includes physical, mental, and social wellbeing and resilience, rather than just the mere absence of disease”.⁸²

The UK, through its international obligations, has an obligation to protect the right to health, though this right is not specified under domestic law.

4.2.2. Basic legal terms and demarcations used nationally

This section explores the basic legal terms and demarcations used and relevant to the discussion on regulation of HET. We used the following dichotomies as research guidance: medical versus non-medical, treatment versus enhancement, therapeutic versus non-therapeutic, natural versus non-natural.

There are various relevant terms to take into account in the discussions on HET regulation. These include definitions of ‘medicinal product’, ‘medical device’, ‘active implantable medical device’, ‘non-medicinal products’ etc.

The Human Medicines Regulations 2012⁸³ define a “**medicinal product**” as (a) any substance or combination of substances presented as having properties of preventing or treating disease in human beings; or (b) any substance or combination of substances that may be used by or administered to human beings with a view to (i) restoring, correcting or modifying a physiological function by exerting a pharmacological, immunological or metabolic action, or (ii) making a medical diagnosis.⁸⁴

The Medical Devices Regulations 2002 define a “**medical device**” as an instrument, apparatus, appliance, material or other article, whether used alone or in combination, together with any software necessary for its proper application, which— (a) is intended by the manufacturer to be used for human beings for the purpose of- (i) diagnosis, prevention, monitoring, treatment or alleviation of disease, (ii) diagnosis, monitoring, treatment, alleviation of or compensation for an injury or handicap, (iii) investigation, replacement or modification of the anatomy or of a physiological process, or (iv) control

⁷⁸ This Act consolidates certain enactments relating to the control of disease and to the establishment and functions of port health authorities, including enactments relating to burial and cremation and to the regulation of common lodging-houses and canal boats, with amendments to give effect to recommendations of the Law Commission. <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1984/22>

⁷⁹ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2012/7/contents/enacted>

⁸⁰ Section 1.

⁸¹ Department of Health and Social Care, Public Health, 2018. <https://www.gov.uk/government/topics/public-health>

⁸² NHS Health Scotland, “Our context- public health in Scotland”, 2018. <http://www.healthscotland.scot/our-organisation/our-context-public-health-in-scotland>

⁸³ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2012/1916/regulation/2/made>

⁸⁴ Section 2.

of conception; and (b) does not achieve its principal intended action in or on the human body by pharmacological, immunological or metabolic means, even if it is assisted in its function by such means, and includes devices intended to administer a medicinal product or which incorporate as an integral part a substance which, if used separately, would be a medicinal product and which is liable to act upon the body with action ancillary to that of the device”.

The Regulations also define “**active implantable medical device**”⁸⁵ as a “medical device which— (a) relies for its functioning on a source of electrical energy or a source of power other than that generated directly by the human body or by gravity; and (b) is intended to be totally or partially introduced into the human body (whether surgically or medically, including being introduced into a natural orifice) and which is intended to remain in the human body after completion of the surgical or medical procedure during which it is introduced, even if it is intended to administer a medicinal product or incorporates as an integral part a substance which, if used separately, would be a medicinal product.”

The Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency (MHRA) decides on what is a medicine or medical device (borderline products⁸⁶).⁸⁷ It classifies medical devices into three types:

- medical devices – covered by the Medical Devices Directive (Directive 93/42/EEC)
- in vitro diagnostic medical devices – covered by the In Vitro Diagnostic Medical Devices (Directive 98/79/EC)
- active implantable medical devices – covered by the Active Implantable Medical Devices (Directive 90/385/EEC).

The MHRA clarifies that to decide whether a product is considered to be a medical device or a medicinal product, the following points are taken into consideration:

- the intended purpose of the product taking into account the way the product is presented;
- the method by which the principal intended action is achieved.⁸⁸

It further outlines that “The principle mode of action for a medical device is typically fulfilled by physical means (including mechanical action, physical barrier, replacement of, or support to, organs or body functions)”.⁸⁹ It also notes that “Medical devices may contain medicinal substances, including herbal and plant extracts and substances derived from human blood or blood plasma, which act on the body

⁸⁵ Examples include implantable cardiac pacemakers, implantable defibrillators, leads, electrodes, adaptors for the above, implantable nerve stimulators, bladder stimulators, sphincter stimulators, diaphragm stimulators, cochlear implants, implantable active drug administration device, catheters, sensors for item above, Implantable active monitoring devices, programmers, software, transmitters.

⁸⁶ i.e., products on the borderline between medicinal products and food supplements, biocides, cosmetic products, medical devices or general products. These products are called borderline products until their status has been decided.

⁸⁷ MHRA, *Guidance: Decide if your product is a medicine or a medical device*, 2013. <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/decide-if-your-product-is-a-medicine-or-a-medical-device#types-of-borderline-products>

⁸⁸ Ibid.

⁸⁹ https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/521420/Borderlines_between_medical_devices_and_other_products_such_as_personal_protective_equipment_cosmetics_and_biocides.pdf

in a manner ancillary to the device. However, when such substances act in a manner that is more than ancillary, the product is likely to be regulated as a medicinal product.”⁹⁰

Non-medicinal products are seen as “Products containing chemicals or substances that were primarily developed for non-medicinal purposes, such as for industrial (e.g., chemical) processes or agricultural use, and which have no valid use in clinical practice...”⁹¹

Treatment versus enhancement

Medical treatment was defined in the Mental Health Act 1983 (s. 145). This was amended by the Mental Health Act 2007. Accordingly, medical treatment now includes nursing, psychological intervention and specialist mental health habilitation, rehabilitation and care. The Mental Health Act 2007 clarifies that “reference in the Act to medical treatment, in relation to mental disorder, shall be construed as a reference to medical treatment the purpose of which is to alleviate, or prevent a worsening of, the disorder or one or more of its symptoms or manifestations.”⁹² The Acts do not specifically mention enhancement.

Therapeutic versus non-therapeutic

It was extremely difficult to find explicit distinctions or clear-cut clarifications of differences between ‘therapeutic’ and ‘non-therapeutic’. We found some relevant information in the Manual of Patent Practice.⁹³ The Manual says the term ‘therapy’ includes “prevention as well as the treatment or cure of disease as held by the Patents Court in Unilever Limited (Davis’) Application⁹⁴” (noting that medical dictionaries cited point towards a narrow interpretation of the term). It outlines that “for a treatment to constitute therapy there must be a direct link between the treatment and disease state being cured, prevented or alleviated”.⁹⁵ It further suggests that “any medical treatment of a disease, ailment, injury or disability, i.e., anything that is wrong with a patient and for which he would consult a doctor, as well as prophylactic treatments such as vaccination and inoculation, is to be regarded as therapy”.⁹⁶

4.2.3. Criteria to classify services, devices and products

The MHRA decides if a product is a medicine in the following cases⁹⁷:

⁹⁰ MHRA, *A Guide to what is a medicinal product*, MHRA Guidance note 8, March 2016. https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/506397/a_guide_to_what_is_a_medicinal_product.pdf

⁹¹ MHRA, *A Guide to what is a medicinal product*, MHRA Guidance note 8, March 2016. https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/506397/a_guide_to_what_is_a_medicinal_product.pdf

⁹² Section 7(2), Mental Health Act 2007.

⁹³ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/patents-manual-of-patent-practice>

⁹⁴ [1983] RPC 219

⁹⁵ Intellectual Property Office, *Manual of Patent Practice*, 2016. <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/manual-of-patent-practice-mopp/-section-4a-methods-of-treatment-or-diagnosis>

⁹⁶ Intellectual Property Office, *Manual of Patent Practice*, 2016. <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/manual-of-patent-practice-mopp/-section-4a-methods-of-treatment-or-diagnosis>

⁹⁷ Noting that “The MHRA can only decide if a product is or is not a medicinal product and cannot classify products that fall under other product legislation. Compliance with other product regulations should be

- the manufacturer is not sure if their product is a medicine or not, and they come to MHRA for advice
- MHRA receives a complaint that a product is being marketed as a medicine but does not have a marketing authorisation (formerly a product licence).⁹⁸

It does this by looking at:

- the claims about what the product does (explicit and implicit)
- the pharmacological, metabolic or immunological properties of the ingredients (this includes any herbal ingredients)
- the primary intended purpose of the product
- whether there are any similar licensed or registered products on the market
- how it is presented to the public through labelling, packaging, promotional literature and advertisements.⁹⁹

According to MHRA Guidance, borderline products may include cosmetics, food products, including, in particular, food supplements, herbal products, medical devices, biocides and machinery/laboratory equipment. The MHRA also clarifies that there is a “borderline between medicinal products and medical devices. In these cases it will be the claims being made and the mode of action that will decide which regulatory regime will apply.”¹⁰⁰

The MHRA explains that medical devices are classified based on the level of risk associated with them, i.e., the strictest control is for products with the highest risk. There are classes associated with general medical devices, i.e.,¹⁰¹

- Class I - generally regarded as low risk
- Class IIa - generally regarded as medium risk
- Class IIb - generally regarded as medium risk
- Class III - generally regarded as high risk

How a medical device is classified depends on factors including the **intended purpose of the device**, how long it’s intended to be in use and if the device:¹⁰²

- is invasive/ surgically invasive,
- is implantable or active,
- contains a substance, which in its own right is considered to be a medicinal substance.

checked with the appropriate authority.” p. 13.

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/506397/a_guide_to_what_is_a_medicinal_product.pdf

⁹⁸ MHRA, op. cit., 2013. According to the Human Medicines Regulations 2012 Regulations, “a person may not publish an advertisement for a medicinal product unless one of the following is in force for the product - (a) marketing authorisation; (b) a certificate of registration; (c) a traditional herbal registration; or (d) an Article 126a authorisation. This refers to an authorisation granted by the licensing authority under Part 8 of these Regulations”.

⁹⁹ MHRA, op. cit., 2013

¹⁰⁰ MHRA, “Guidance: Decide if your product is a medicine or a medical device”, 21 June 2013.

<https://www.gov.uk/guidance/decide-if-your-product-is-a-medicine-or-a-medical-device>

¹⁰¹ MHRA, “Medical devices: how to comply with the legal requirements”, 16 August 2013.
<https://www.gov.uk/guidance/medical-devices-how-to-comply-with-the-legal-requirements>

¹⁰² MHRA, “Medical devices: how to comply with the legal requirements”, 16 August 2013.
<https://www.gov.uk/guidance/medical-devices-how-to-comply-with-the-legal-requirements>

Accessories to medical devices are classified separately to the device, excluding accessories to active implantable devices.¹⁰³

The MHRA 2014 guidance on borderlines with medical devices presents the MHRA's views on the interpretation of the medical devices legislation as it relates to borderline products.¹⁰⁴ This clarifies,

In general, medical devices must have a 'medical purpose' which is determined by the definition of a medical device. They must also act primarily in a way that is not metabolic, immunological or pharmacological. Should they function in any way that is metabolic, immunological or pharmacological, in conjunction with having a medical purpose, they are likely to come within the remit of the regulations covering medicinal products instead.¹⁰⁵

The MHRA states that "not all equipment used in a healthcare environment or used by a healthcare professional will be considered to come within the definition of a medical device".¹⁰⁶ Further, "As medical devices are considered to be specifically intended for a 'medical purpose', products that do not have such a principal intended purpose are not considered to be medical devices, even if they may be considered to be used for the prevention of disease as a secondary purpose."¹⁰⁷ For example, muscle toning products are not normally considered to be a medical device, but if there is a specific primary intended medical purpose, similar products may be considered to be medical devices, e.g., muscle toning products with medical claims (such as treatment of incontinence).¹⁰⁸

Further, the MHRA states that "equipment intended for alleviation of, or compensation for a disability may or may not be considered as medical devices. The determining factor will be whether or not there is a direct link between the corrective function of the equipment and the individual concerned and that there is a stated medical purpose."¹⁰⁹ In general, products for sport or leisure purposes are not considered to be medical devices but in some cases, products aimed at sports people may be considered to be medical devices, e.g., where specific claims are made for the treatment of pain or

¹⁰³ MHRA, "Medical devices: how to comply with the legal requirements", 16 August 2013.
<https://www.gov.uk/guidance/medical-devices-how-to-comply-with-the-legal-requirements>

¹⁰⁴ MHRA, "Guidance on legislation: Borderlines with medical devices", February 2014.
https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/284505/B_orderlines_with_medical_devices.pdf

¹⁰⁵ MHRA, "Guidance on legislation: Borderlines with medical devices", February 2014.
https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/284505/B_orderlines_with_medical_devices.pdf

¹⁰⁶ MHRA, "Guidance on legislation: Borderlines with medical devices", February 2014.
https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/284505/B_orderlines_with_medical_devices.pdf

¹⁰⁷ MHRA, "Guidance on legislation: Borderlines with medical devices", February 2014.
https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/284505/B_orderlines_with_medical_devices.pdf

¹⁰⁸ MHRA, "Guidance on legislation: Borderlines with medical devices", February 2014.
https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/284505/B_orderlines_with_medical_devices.pdf

¹⁰⁹ MHRA, "Guidance on legislation: Borderlines with medical devices", February 2014.
https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/284505/B_orderlines_with_medical_devices.pdf

injury and the product acts in a physical manner.¹¹⁰ Where products may appear to have a medical purpose, but in fact are designed to protect the use, these are usually considered to be personal protective equipment (PPE) rather than medical devices. This depends on the intended purpose for the individual product concerned.¹¹¹ For further information on other categories, refer to the MHRA Guidance.

4.3 Right to integrity of the person and legal permissibility of non-therapeutic services on the human body

This section first examines whether domestic law recognises the right to (physical and/or mental) integrity of the person. It next looks at the legality of enhancement procedures. It then examines whether there are limits to what non-therapeutic procedures can be performed on a human body, criteria used to establish those limits, role of consent and how the law deals with risks and benefits. Another issue is whether there is a legal requirement for informed consent in the case of all non-therapeutic procedures. Finally, it considers whether protection afforded to the augmented or modified body (e.g., body with prosthetics) has been addressed nationally.

4.3.1 *Does the domestic law recognize the right to (physical and/or mental) integrity of the person? If yes, please provide a relevant citation. What are the limits to this right? Please provide examples. What criteria and values are considered to set those limits?*

A right to bodily integrity¹¹² has been considered as “the most important of civil rights”¹¹³ and as “the first and most important of the interests protected by the law of tort”.¹¹⁴ In *Re A (Conjoined Twins)*, Walker L.J. stated it thusly:

Every human being’s right to life carries with it, as an intrinsic part of it, rights of bodily integrity and autonomy – the right to have one’s own body whole and intact and (on reaching an age of understanding) to take decisions about one’s own body.¹¹⁵

¹¹⁰ MHRA, “Guidance on legislation: Borderlines with medical devices”, February 2014.

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/284505/B_orderlines_with_medical_devices.pdf

¹¹¹ MHRA, “Guidance on legislation: Borderlines with medical devices”, February 2014.

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/284505/B_orderlines_with_medical_devices.pdf

¹¹² Defined by David Feldman as “a right to be free from physical interference”. Feldman, D., *Civil Liberties and Human Rights in England and Wales*, Oxford, 2002, p. 241.

¹¹³ *R. (on the application of Justin West) v The Parole Board* [2002] EWCA Civ 1641; [2003] 1 W.L.R. 705, at [49], per Hale L.J. in her dissenting judgment.

¹¹⁴ *Parkinson v St. James NHS Trust* [2001] EWCA 530; [2002] Q.B. 266.

¹¹⁵ *Re A (Conjoined Twins)* [2001] Fam. 147, at 258, per Walker L.J.

Herring and Wall suggest that, “Although the concept of bodily integrity has played a significant role in the academic literature, it has received relatively little attention in the courts”.¹¹⁶ Further, they underline that the “blurring between bodily autonomy and bodily integrity is a common aspect of the case law”.¹¹⁷ The most significant and landmark judgment is *Montgomery v Lanarkshire Health Board*¹¹⁸ where Lord Kerr and Lord Reed reasoned “that an adult of sound mind is entitled to decide which, if any, of the available treatments to undergo, and her consent must be obtained before treatment interfering with her bodily integrity is undertaken”.¹¹⁹ The novelty in this case was that the requirement for consent was enhanced; clinicians have a duty to inform the service user prior to consent based on her or his personal priorities and concerns. This is a patient-centred test and not a ‘reasonable’ test¹²⁰.

The Court of Appeal in *R. (on the application of Nicklinson) v Ministry of Justice*,¹²¹ pointed to some cases that had closely related the right of someone to choose how to spend their life as involving “individual autonomy or the right to self-determination” as closely related to “respect for the dignity of the individual human being.” Though the Court of Appeal expressed some doubts about “whether autonomy and dignity can properly be described as independent common law rights rather than values or principles which inform more specific common law rights such as the right to bodily integrity and privacy”, it stated that it did “not under-estimate the importance of these concepts in the structure of the law”. The Court conceded the premise that they could in principle be so described for the purposes of analysing the case.¹²²

Herring and Wall’s discussion of the concept of bodily integrity concludes that “the courts place considerable store by the concept of the right to bodily integrity, protected both as a common law right and under the ECHR. However, there is little guidance on the content or nature of the right. In some cases it seems indistinguishable from a general autonomy right, and it is far from clear what the contours of the right are.”¹²³ Another key point Herring and Wall make is that the right to bodily integrity is also a specific right, and that is protected by law through criminal provisions and tortious actions – giving legal effect to a person exclusive use and control over his or her body (with some exceptions).¹²⁴

Under the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights (which as of writing applies to matters concerning EU Law but it can be raised in courts in the UK on such matters), everyone has the right to respect for his or her physical and mental integrity.

¹¹⁶ Herring, Jonathan, and Jesse Wall, “The Nature and Significance of the Right to Bodily Integrity”, *The Cambridge Law Journal*, Vol. 76, Iss. 3, 2017, pp. 566-588 [p. 569]

¹¹⁷ Herring and Wall, op. cit., 2017, p 570. Citing the cases of *NHS Trust A v M*; *NHS Trust B v H* [2001] Fam. 348, at [41], quoted with apparent approval in *Re Y and Z (Children)* [2013] EWHC 953 (Fam); and the speech of Arden L.J. in *Evans v Amicus Healthcare Ltd.* [2004] EWCA Civ 727; [2005] Fam. 1.

¹¹⁸ [2015] UKSC 11; [2015] 1 A.C. 1430.

¹¹⁹ Ibid.

¹²⁰ This is a big discussion dating back to Bolam and Chester decisions. See *Bolam v Friern Hospital Management Committee* [1957] 2 All ER 118. *Chester v Afshar* [2004] 4 All E.R. 587

¹²¹ *R. (on the application of Nicklinson) v Ministry of Justice* [2013] EWCA Civ 961; [2015] 1 A.C. 657 (upheld on appeal: [2014] UKSC 38; [2015] A.C. 657.

¹²² *R. (on the application of Nicklinson) v Ministry of Justice* [2013] EWCA Civ 961

¹²³ Herring, Jonathan, and Jesse Wall, “The Nature and Significance of the Right to Bodily Integrity”, *The Cambridge Law Journal*, Vol. 76, Iss. 3, 2017, pp. 566-588, p. 575.

¹²⁴ Herring and Wall, op. cit., 2017, p. 584.

The European Court of Human Rights in *Pretty v United Kingdom*¹²⁵ stated: “As the Court has had previous occasion to remark, the concept of ‘private life’ is a broad term not susceptible to exhaustive definition. It covers the physical and psychological integrity of a person”. The respect for physical and psychological integrity forms part of the right to respect for private life in Article 8 ECHR (which is given effect in the domestic law of the UK through the Human Rights Act 1998 and through the devolution statutes).

4.3.2 *How is the legality of enhancement procedures (understood as non-therapeutic interventions in the human body) established?*

The legality of enhancement procedures is not entirely clear-cut, as there is no blanket or overarching regulation that is applicable given the variant nature of such procedures, as explained below, and under what they might be classed. The nature of enhancement procedures on offer is often unclear, and (especially in private clinics) might vary and change with medical and technological progress, which makes it a challenge for (effective) regulation. As the NHS indicates, complementary therapies (that fall outside mainstream healthcare might be legal in the sense that anyone may practise the treatment even if they have no or limited formal qualifications or experience and these practitioners are not legally required to adhere to any standards of practice or to join an association or register.”¹²⁶ So some interventions might be permitted to the extent that there is no ban on them.

Of particular relevance here is the Keogh report (2013)¹²⁷ which reviewed regulation in the cosmetic interventions (surgical¹²⁸ and non-surgical¹²⁹) sector following the PIP implant scandal. Of particular relevance is its finding that non-surgical interventions (accounting for 75% of the market value of the cosmetic interventions market, “which can have major and irreversible adverse impacts on health and wellbeing, are almost entirely unregulated”.¹³⁰ The report further outlines that “*a person having a non-surgical cosmetic intervention has no more protection and redress than someone buying a ballpoint pen or a toothbrush*” (italics supplied).¹³¹ The report’s key recommendations focussed on high quality care, informing and empowering the public and accessible resolution and redress.

¹²⁵ (Application no. 2346/02), Judgment, Strasbourg, 29 April 2002.

¹²⁶ <https://www.nhs.uk/conditions/complementary-and-alternative-medicine/>

¹²⁷ Department of Health, “Review of the Regulation of Cosmetic Interventions”, April 2013.

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/192028/Review_of_the_Regulation_of_Cosmetic_Interventions.pdf

¹²⁸ These include face-lifts, tummy tucks and breast implants.

¹²⁹ These include dermal fillers, Botox® or the use of laser or intense pulsed light (IPL).

¹³⁰ Department of Health, “Review of the Regulation of Cosmetic Interventions”, April 2013.

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/192028/Review_of_the_Regulation_of_Cosmetic_Interventions.pdf

¹³¹ Department of Health, “Review of the Regulation of Cosmetic Interventions”, April 2013.

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/192028/Review_of_the_Regulation_of_Cosmetic_Interventions.pdf

The government response to the Keogh report¹³² outlined measures on which the government was working with healthcare regulators and patient safety organisations to improve the quality of training and care provided by the industry to practitioners and patients. It also agreed that:

- the responsibility of prescribing professionals should be emphasised by professional regulators in their codes and action taken if practice does not conform to expectations;
- those administering and supervising cosmetic interventions should be appropriately trained and accountable. Non-healthcare practitioners administering cosmetic interventions should be properly trained and, where appropriate, work under the supervision of a regulated professional;
- the products used in cosmetic interventions should be more closely controlled and monitored;
- to begin with, breast implants, but eventually all implanted devices including dermal fillers, should be monitored; and
- those who choose to undergo a cosmetic intervention should have access to all the relevant information in order to give informed consent and have recourse to adequate redress in the event of something going wrong.¹³³

The UK General Medical Council has guidance on cosmetic interventions¹³⁴ that incorporates principles from its existing guidance, and is structured under the four domains of *Good medical practice*. To maintain their licence to practise, doctors must demonstrate, through the revalidation process, that they work in line with the principles and values set out in the guidance (along with other relevant guidance¹³⁵). Serious or persistent failure to follow this guidance will put their registration at risk.

The Advertising Standards Authority (ASA) has cracked down on irresponsible advertising and aggressive inducements of cosmetic interventions (in this case, “the overall presentation of the ad was likely to be seen as trivialising breast enhancement surgery”).¹³⁶

Complementary and alternative medicines (CAMs) are treatments that fall outside of mainstream healthcare.¹³⁷ These include homeopathy, acupuncture, osteopathy, chiropractic and herbal medicines. Of these only chiropractic and osteopathic practice is regulated by statutory professional regulation.

¹³² Department of Health, “Government response to the review of the regulation of cosmetic interventions”, 2014.

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/279431/Government_response_to_the_review_of_the_regulation_of_cosmetic_interventions.pdf

¹³³ Department of Health, “Government response to the review of the regulation of cosmetic interventions”, 2014.

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/279431/Government_response_to_the_review_of_the_regulation_of_cosmetic_interventions.pdf

¹³⁴ General Medical Council, “Guidance for doctors who offer cosmetic interventions”

<https://www.gmc-uk.org/ethical-guidance/ethical-guidance-for-doctors/cosmetic-interventions/about-this-guidance?>

¹³⁵ E.g., Professional Standards for Cosmetic Surgery - Royal College of Surgeons (2016), Marketing of cosmetic interventions - Committee of Advertising Practice (2016), The British Association of Aesthetic Plastic Surgeons code of practice.

¹³⁶ General Medical Council, “Guidance for doctors who offer cosmetic interventions”. <https://www.gmc-uk.org/ethical-guidance/ethical-guidance-for-doctors/cosmetic-interventions/about-this-guidance>

¹³⁷ <https://www.nhs.uk/conditions/complementary-and-alternative-medicine/>

4.3.3 Are there limits to what non-therapeutic procedures can be performed on a human body? What criteria are used to establish those limits? What is the role of consent? Does the national law, case-law or legal doctrine provide any guidance on how risks and benefits of non-therapeutic procedures should be weighed and/or what is the acceptable level of risk in those cases?

As to the extent of what limits there are on non-therapeutic procedures (i.e., those where there is no direct link between treatment and a disease state being cured, prevented or alleviated), that can be performed on the human body, we examined this in the context of the Health and Social Care Act 2008 (Regulated Activities) Regulations 2014.¹³⁸

The Health and Social Care Act 2008 (Regulated Activities) Regulations 2014 (applicable to England) (*hereinafter, in this section, The Regulations*) sets out the health and social care activities that are to be “regulated activities” for the purposes of the Health and Social Care Act 2008 (“the Act”). Regulated activities are subject to regulation by the Care Quality Commission which is responsible for regulating providers of regulated activities. The Regulations outline a single regulatory framework across health and social care services; they set out the regulated activities (providers of these need to register with the Commission) and list the registration requirements¹³⁹ under the full registration system. Under the Act, regulated activities include: personal care, accommodation for persons who require nursing or personal care, accommodation for persons who require treatment for substance misuse, accommodation and nursing or personal care in the further education sector, treatment of disease, disorder or injury (by or under the supervision of a health care professional, or a multi-disciplinary team that includes a healthcare professional; or a social worker, or a multi-disciplinary team that includes a social worker, where the treatment is for a mental disorder), assessment or medical treatment for persons detained under the 1983 Act, surgical procedures, diagnostic and screening procedures, management of supply of blood and blood-derived products, transport services, triage and medical advice provided remotely, maternity and midwifery services, termination of pregnancies, services in slimming clinics, nursing care, and family planning services.

The Regulations outline specific requirements for persons carrying on or managing a regulated activity. They set out quality and safety of service provisions in relation to regulated activity. Aspects covered include: care and welfare of service users, assessing and monitoring the quality of service provision, safeguarding service users from abuse, cleanliness and infection control, management of medicines, meeting nutritional needs, safety and suitability of premises, safety, availability and suitability of equipment (includes a medical device), respecting and involving service users¹⁴⁰, consent to care and

¹³⁸ These Regulations supersede (and revoke) earlier Regulations and put in place an expanded registration system to cover a wider range of regulated activities and impose an increased number of registration requirements.

¹³⁹ I.e., the requirements relating to persons carrying on or managing a regulated activity, and what a provider will need to do in relation to the quality and safety of services provided in order to register and stay registered with the Commission.

¹⁴⁰ I.e., making suitable arrangements to ensure dignity, privacy and independence of service users. Service users should be able to make, or participate in making, decisions relating to their care or treatment. The registered

treatment¹⁴¹, complaints, records, requirements relating to workers, staffing, supporting workers, and co-operating with other providers.

The Regulations (regulation 11) also deal with the need for consent and provide that care and treatment of service users must only be provided with the consent of the relevant person. If the service user is 16 or over and is unable to give such consent because they lack capacity to do so, the registered person must act in accordance with the Mental Capacity 2005 Act (or if Part 4 or 4A of the 1983 Act applies to a service user, the registered person must act in accordance with the provisions of that Act).

The Regulations (regulation 12) explains what must be done by registered persons to comply with their duty of safe care and treatment: i.e., assessing the risks to the health and safety of service users receiving the care or treatment; doing all that is reasonably practicable to mitigate such risks; ensuring that persons providing care or treatment to service users have the qualifications, competence, skills and experience to do so safely; ensuring that the premises used by the service provider are safe to use for their intended purpose and are used in a safe way; ensuring that the equipment used by the service provider for providing care or treatment to a service user is safe for such use and is used in a safe way; where equipment or medicines are supplied by the service provider, ensuring that there are sufficient quantities of these to ensure the safety of service users and to meet their needs; the proper and safe management of medicines; assessing the risk of, and preventing, detecting and controlling the spread of, infections, including those that are health care associated; where responsibility for the care and treatment of service users is shared with, or transferred to, other persons, working with such other persons, service users and other appropriate persons to ensure that timely care planning takes place to ensure the health, safety and welfare of the service users.

Contravention of the Regulations (9-24) is an offence that can lead to a fine not exceeding £50,000 on summary conviction. The Regulations also prescribe fixed penalty offences.

Under the Local Government (Miscellaneous Provisions) Act 1982, as amended, local authorities are responsible for regulating and monitoring businesses offering cosmetic body piercing (including ear piercing), permanent tattooing, semi-permanent skin colouring (micropigmentation, semi-permanent make-up and temporary tattooing), electrolysis and acupuncture. Such activities are regulated as they carry a risk of harm to the body. The focus of legislation covering local authorities in England, Wales

person should treat service users with consideration and respect; provide service users with appropriate information and support in relation to their care or treatment; encourage service users, or those acting on their behalf, to (i) understand the care or treatment choices available to the service user, and discuss with an appropriate health care professional, or other appropriate person, the balance of risks and benefits involved in any particular course of care or treatment, and (ii) express their views as to what is important to them in relation to the care or treatment; where necessary, assist service users, or those acting on their behalf, to express their views; where appropriate, provide opportunities for service users to manage their own care or treatment; where appropriate, involve service users in decisions relating to the way in which the regulated activity is carried on in so far as it relates to their care or treatment; provide appropriate opportunities, encouragement and support to service users in relation to promoting their autonomy, independence and community involvement; and take care to ensure that care and treatment is provided to service users with due regard to their age, sex, religious persuasion, sexual orientation, racial origin, cultural and linguistic background and any disability they may have.

¹⁴¹ The registered person must have suitable arrangements in place for obtaining, and acting in accordance with, the consent of service users in relation to the care and treatment provided for them.

and Northern Ireland is on minimising infection risks using compulsory registration of practitioners and premises and optional powers to make byelaws.¹⁴² Under all current legislation, it is a criminal offence to trade without registration (licensing) or to be in breach of the relevant byelaws. The Department of Health has produced guidance¹⁴³ for local authorities regulating piercing and tattooing businesses, and model byelaws for the use of local authorities. The Tattooing Of Minors Act 1969 prohibits the tattooing of persons under the age of eighteen years (though it is a defence for a person charged with violating the Act to show that at the time the tattoo was performed he had reasonable cause to believe that the person tattooed was of or over the age of eighteen and did in fact so believe). Interested persons need to contact the local council where the premises are based to get a tattoo, piercing and electrolysis licence.¹⁴⁴ The license covers tattooing, semi-permanent skin colouring, cosmetic piercing, electrolysis and acupuncture. Both the person offering the procedure and the premises have to be registered.

One example of the lack of clarity with regard to the limits on non-therapeutic procedures that can be performed is evident in the case of DIY (do it yourself) human enhancement – where human enhancement and augmentation is or might be carried out in privately (e.g., in the home) and where the reach of the law might not extend due to the lack of visibility of such actions. The law protects a person against harms caused to her or him by another (e.g., trespass to person, negligence, bodily injury or assault), but it is still not very clear whether or how the law should treat someone who has self-enhanced to their own detriment or perceived benefit. But the detriment or benefit might not exclusively play a role in liability; the nature of the operation or activity is crucial. If an activity is forbidden or heavily restricted and a service provider and user breach the law, both would bear liability (e.g., medical termination of pregnancy is permitted subject to the provisions outlined in the Abortion Act 1967. Abortion is not legal in Northern Ireland except when there is a serious risk to mental or physical health and the risk is permanent or long term, as outlined in the Protection of Life During Pregnancy Act 2013).

4.3.4 Is there a legal requirement for informed consent in the case of all non-therapeutic procedures? If yes, are requirements concerning informed consent more or less rigorous than in the case of procedures with a therapeutic aim?

The UK does not have a doctrine of informed consent.¹⁴⁵ Reynard and Marsh outline, “the process of obtaining consent for treatment of the competent adult is governed by common law, i.e., by case law, rather than by statute”.¹⁴⁶ They further outline that “ by contrast with the legal obligation to obtain consent, regulatory requirements laid down by the General Medical Council (GMC) are, in many ways,

¹⁴² Smith, Louise, “Regulation of tattooing and body piercing businesses”, Commons Briefing papers SN05079, 12 May 2010. <https://researchbriefings.parliament.uk/ResearchBriefing/Summary/SN05079#fullreport>

¹⁴³ Public Health England, *Tattooing and body piercing guidance toolkit*, July 2013.

<https://www.cieh.org/media/2004/tattooing-and-body-piercing-guidance-toolkit-july-2013.pdf>

¹⁴⁴ <https://www.gov.uk/skin-piercing-and-tattooing>

¹⁴⁵ Goold, Imogen, “The legal aspects of cognitive enhancement,” in Ruud ter Meulen, Ahmed Mohamed, and Wayne Hall (eds.), *Rethinking Cognitive Enhancement*, Oxford University Press 2017, pp. 250-273 [p. 270]

¹⁴⁶ Reynard, John, and Howard Marsh, “The development of consent from Bolam to Chester: what you need to know and what your patients are entitled to know”, *BJU international*, Vol. 103, Iss. 11, 2009, pp. 1458-1461

more onerous. A breach of GMC guidance has far more serious implications for the surgeon than those that a civil court might impose.”¹⁴⁷

The GMC reiterates that the “law relating to decision-making and consent, particularly for patients who lack capacity, varies across the UK, doctors need to understand the law as it applies where they work”.¹⁴⁸ The standard of informed consent was developed in case law and it continues to develop and indeed, the standards and conditions of informed consent vary across the UK. The basic acts for people lacking capacity to consent include the Adults with Incapacity (Scotland) Act 2000 and Mental Capacity Act 2005. These acts codified the common law. Common law continues to apply under an age threshold. It is important to distinguish: If a person has capacity to consent and is not provided information at all, then s/he can bring action in battery. If insufficient information is provided, the action in negligence is appropriate.

In regard to consent to treatment, the NHS website explains:¹⁴⁹

Consent to treatment is the principle that a person must give permission before they receive any type of medical treatment, test or examination. This must be done on the basis of an explanation by a clinician. Consent from a patient is needed regardless of the procedure, whether it's a physical examination, organ donation or something else. The principle of consent is an important part of medical ethics and the international human rights law.

It outlines that “For consent to be valid, it must be voluntary¹⁵⁰ and informed¹⁵¹, and the person consenting must have the capacity¹⁵² to make the decision”. It further states:

an adult has the capacity to make a voluntary and informed decision to consent to or refuse a particular treatment, their decision must be respected. This is still the case even if refusing treatment would result in their death, or the death of their unborn child. If a person doesn't have the capacity to make a decision about their treatment, and they haven't appointed a lasting power of attorney (LPA), the healthcare professionals treating them can go ahead and give treatment if they believe it's in the person's best interests. But clinicians must take reasonable steps to seek advice from the patient's friends or relatives before making these decisions.¹⁵³

Consent can be given verbally, non-verbally or in writing and should be given to the healthcare professional directly responsible for the person's current treatment, e.g., the nurse, general practitioner or surgeon. In the cases of major medical procedures (e.g., operations) the NHS explains that their consent should ideally be secured well in advance, so they have plenty of time to obtain information about the procedure and ask questions. If the person changes their mind at any point before the procedure, they are entitled to withdraw their previous consent). Persons with parental

¹⁴⁷ Reynard and Marsh, op. cit., 2009.

¹⁴⁸ General Medical Council, “Consent: patients and doctors making decisions together”, 2008.

https://www.gmc-uk.org/-/media/documents/consent---english-0617_pdf-48903482.pdf

¹⁴⁹ NHS, “Consent to treatment”, Undated. <https://www.nhs.uk/conditions/consent-to-treatment/>

¹⁵⁰ I.e., the decision to either consent or not to consent to treatment must be made by the person themselves, and must not be influenced by pressure from medical staff, friends or family

¹⁵¹ I.e., the person must be given all of the information in terms of what the treatment involves, including the benefits and risks, whether there are reasonable alternative treatments, and what will happen if treatment doesn't go ahead

¹⁵² I.e., the person must be capable of giving consent, which means they understand the information given to them and they can use it to make an informed decision

¹⁵³ NHS, “Consent to treatment”, Undated. <https://www.nhs.uk/conditions/consent-to-treatment/>

responsibility may need to give consent for a child up to the age of 16 to have treatment. Note that, as explained by the BMA, “in England, Wales and Northern Ireland there are some rare procedures – for example, live organ donation, some non-therapeutic procedures and research – where the presumption of competence for 16-17 year olds does not apply. A 16-17 year old is only deemed competent if *Gillick* competent. These exceptions do not apply to Scotland where a young person over the age of 16 is treated as an adult.”¹⁵⁴ The case of *Gillick v. West Norfolk & Wisbech Area Health Authority*¹⁵⁵ held that if a child under the age of 18 can show that they have sufficient maturity to make the decision in question then they will be deemed able to provide their own elective consent to treatment. This can, however, be overridden where there is a treatment need.¹⁵⁶

In cases of cosmetic interventions, the responsibility for seeking consent falls on the doctor carrying out the intervention. Doctors must discuss with their patients the interventions and must not delegate this responsibility. The GMC clarifies that “it is essential to a shared understanding of expectations and limitations that consent to a cosmetic intervention is sought by the doctor who will perform it, or supervise its performance by another practitioner.”¹⁵⁷ Doctors carrying out cosmetic interventions have to follow the GMC guidance on *Consent: patients and doctors making decisions together*¹⁵⁸. Doctors have to discuss with prospective patients seeking an intervention their medical history, why they would like to have the intervention and the outcome they hope for, before assessing whether the intervention is appropriate and likely to meet their needs. They must also inform the patient if the intervention is unlikely to deliver the desired outcome or to be of overall benefit to the patient. If it’s of no benefit to the patient, doctors must not provide the intervention and discuss other options. Doctors have to inform patients about monitoring or follow-up care requirements at the outset and advise patients if implanted medical devices may need to be removed or replaced and after how long. They also have to advise patients of the availability of alternative less risky interventions, including from other practitioners. Doctors have to give patients clear, accurate information about the risks and adverse outcomes. Further, the GMC clarifies that patients must be given all the information they need to reach a voluntary and informed decision about whether to go ahead with an intervention depending on several factors: invasiveness, complexity, permanence and risks of the intervention, how many intervention options the patient is considering and how much information they have already considered about a proposed intervention.¹⁵⁹

The *Tattooing and body piercing guidance toolkit*¹⁶⁰ underlines that practitioners have to ensure that a fully ‘informed consent’ procedure is adopted. They should gather information from the client about

¹⁵⁴ British Medical Association, Card 4, Consent and refusal. https://www.bma.org.uk/-/media/files/pdfs/.../childrenyoungpeopletoolkit_card4.pdf

¹⁵⁵ [1986] AC 112 (HL)

¹⁵⁶ In *Re R* [1991] 4 All ER 177, [24H] (CA), Lord Donaldson made it clear that a child’s refusal of consent could be overridden by the provision of another valid consent (for example, that of their parents), a view reiterated in *Re W (A Minor) (Medical Treatment: Court’s Jurisdiction)* [1993] FLR 64, 88 (Fam)

¹⁵⁷ General Medical Council, “Guidance for doctors who offer cosmetic interventions”. <https://www.gmc-uk.org/ethical-guidance/ethical-guidance-for-doctors/cosmetic-interventions>

¹⁵⁸ General Medical Council, *Consent: patients and doctors making decisions together*, 2008. <https://www.gmc-uk.org/ethical-guidance/ethical-guidance-for-doctors/consent>

¹⁵⁹ <https://www.gmc-uk.org/ethical-guidance/ethical-guidance-for-doctors/cosmetic-interventions/communication-partnership-and-teamwork#paragraph-15>

¹⁶⁰ Public Health England, *Tattooing and body piercing guidance toolkit*, July 2013. <https://www.cieh.org/media/2004/tattooing-and-body-piercing-guidance-toolkit-july-2013.pdf>

their health and suitability for the treatment, and give the client enough information about the possible complications that could arise from the treatment for them to make their own decision. Consent should be obtained before treatment takes place, and in the case of a minor, from their parents or legal guardians. Ear or nose piercing is generally acceptable when carried out on a minor, even below the age of five, provided that a parent or legal guardian gives consent and is present whilst the procedure is carried out. The toolkit also provides a consent form template and clarifies that the signing of a declaration and providing proof of age should be a fundamental part of the client consultation process and practitioners should always require that the client signs. Consent is only valid if the customer has been fully informed as to the nature of the process, the likely effect and potential problems involved.¹⁶¹

The Toolkit clarifies that,

semi-permanent skin-colouring, cosmetic piercing, beading, branding, scarring, cutting and other extreme forms of body modification do cause actual harm and generally leave permanent marks and can result in disfigurement. They can therefore be considered as assaults to the body, and so potentially subject to the legislation concerning assault. This means that the question of age and the client's informed consent are very important."¹⁶²

The Toolkit highlights the case of *R v Brown*¹⁶³, where the House of Lords ruled on appeal that consent could not be a defence against sections 20 and 47 of the Offences Against the Person Act 1861 which deals with common assaults. The Toolkit highlights how the law recognises that certain activities that give rise to 'harm' are lawful, i.e., surgery, tattooing, ear piercing and violent sports. As courts have held that children under the age of 18 can consent to cosmetic body piercing provided they are sufficiently mature to understand the nature of the request, it is a "subjective matter for the operator who will need to ensure that the client is provided with sufficient information to allow them to proceed in an informed way and without pressure".¹⁶⁴ The toolkit also highlights that under the Sexual Offences Act 1956, girls and boys under the age of 16 cannot legally consent to intimate sexual contact under any circumstances, so piercing of nipples and genitalia (for girls) or genitalia (for boys) could be regarded as an assault offence. Evidence that such contact was for sexual gratification would be required in order to constitute an indecent assault. The Female Genital Mutilation Act 2003 states that certain procedures in respect of female genitals is illegal unless carried out for medical reasons.

4.3.5 Has the question of the protection afforded to the augmented or modified body (e.g., body with prosthetics) been addressed nationally? Is the augmented or modified body afforded the same protection and guarantees as an organic body? Are there issues regarding ownership?

¹⁶¹ Public Health England, op. cit., 2013.

¹⁶² Public Health England, op. cit., 2013.

¹⁶³ (1994) 1 AC 212

¹⁶⁴ Public Health England, op. cit., 2013.

The question of whether protection afforded to the augmented or modified body¹⁶⁵ (body with prosthetics) has not been addressed nationally as such.

There is some protection in terms of law that governs medical devices. All prosthetic and orthotic device manufacturers have to check if their products meet the criteria for a medical device. The MHRA has further guidance¹⁶⁶ and states that “Manufacturers and healthcare establishments who supply medical devices to be placed on the market either for use or distribution, at a cost or free of charge, must follow the regulations. This applies to new or fully refurbished devices and those not intended for a clinical investigation.”¹⁶⁷ For example, the Ekso GT exoskeleton is CE marked (as a class IIa device) but NICE¹⁶⁸ suggests outlines that “no manufacturer Field Safety Notices or Medical Device Alerts have been issued for this technology”.¹⁶⁹

First, we tackle the question whether the augmented or modified body afforded the same protection and guarantees as an organic body. Quigley and Ayihongbe argue that “the law is ill-equipped to deal with challenges raised by the linking of the organic, biological person with synthetic, inorganic parts and devices”.¹⁷⁰ They further suggest that “the shape of the law should be in this respect remains to be explored and debated”.¹⁷¹ One of the key points Quigley and Ayihongbe make in their analysis pertains to different legislation governing the **synthetic and the biological** - the Medical Devices Regulations 2002 (and now the MDR and IVDR) for artificial devices versus the Human Tissue Acts, (Human Tissue Act 2004, Human Tissue (Scotland) Act 2006), Human Transplantation (Wales) Act 2013, and the Human Fertilisation and Embryology Act 1990 (as amended 2008) for various biomaterials.¹⁷² They further underscore how, “Even within the category of ‘biological’ we can see there is marked boundary-work taking place, most noticeably that which delineates reproductive from other tissues. Thus, for the law it is clear that the types of materials at issue matter. But it is not just that ‘matter matters’; that is, whether it is important that the materials themselves are biological or synthetic. The process of mattering—how material comes to matter—is significant.”¹⁷³ The application of the law is not straightforward as how it, and which law, would apply to protect augmented/modified/synthetic bodies would depend on the individual case. In English law, individuals have no proprietary rights over their body, but control rights.

It could be argued that overall, an augmented or modified body would enjoy protection and guarantees afforded to a human body (e.g., personal injury protection) and may benefit from specific protections afforded to its parts (e.g., patent or copyright protection, protection from illegal

¹⁶⁵ Since initially we found no data using these search terms, we widened the search using terms ‘synthetic person’ and ‘cyborg’.

¹⁶⁶ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/medical-devices-legal-requirements-for-specific-medical-devices/medical-devices-legal-requirements-for-specific-medical-devices>

¹⁶⁷ See also: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/in-house-manufacture-of-medical-devices>

¹⁶⁸ National Institute for Health and Care Excellence.

¹⁶⁹ NICE, “Ekso exoskeleton for rehabilitation in people with neurological weakness or paralysis”, *Medtech innovation briefing* [MIB93], January 2017. <https://www.nice.org.uk/advice/mib93/chapter/Regulatory-information>

¹⁷⁰ Quigley, Muireann, and Semande Ayihongbe, “Everyday Cyborgs: On Integrated Persons and Integrated Goods”, *Medical law review*, Vol. 26, Iss. 2, 2018, pp. 276-308.

¹⁷¹ Quigley and Ayihongbe, op. cit., 2018.

¹⁷² Quigley and Ayihongbe, op. cit., 2018, p. 306.

¹⁷³ Quigley and Ayihongbe, op. cit., 2018, p.306.

interference with wireless communications, product liability protection for prosthesis),¹⁷⁴ though this has not been exactly fully tested in the courts. If a substance or device is integrated into the human body, then it obtains the same status with the body.¹⁷⁵ As Barfield and Williams suggest, “once cyborg devices are viewed by a person as part person as part of their body and very being, the distinction between rights for property versus rights of their body and very being, the distinction between rights for property versus rights for humans for humans becomes blurred and thus doubly important”.¹⁷⁶

Note, however, in *R v Casey Hardison*,¹⁷⁷ the court (upholding the lower court verdict) rejected the argument made by the appellant that an inalienable right to do with our own bodies as we wished included the right to alter our own consciousness by taking drugs whose hallucinogenic qualities free the mind. The appellant had claimed that he was doing no more than enabling members of the human race to expand their horizons by exploring the world through hallucinogenic drugs and its criminalisation was an infringement of his and everyone else's human right to have autonomy over their own person. The Court of Appeal, like its predecessor, found that this was not a defence in law. It stated that the only Convention right properly engaged by this argument was that which guarantees the right to respect for one's private life; however it highlighted citing the case of *Taylor (Paul)*¹⁷⁸, that the prohibitions contained in the Misuse of Drugs Act 1971 did not amount to an unwarranted interference with the appellant's rights to a private life; instead they were part of this country's policy to combat the dangers of narcotic drugs to public health which included international treaty obligations.

Now, we tackle the question of issues regarding ownership. There is no legislation dealing with the ownership of, for example, implanted medical devices. There might be one or many claims to ownership in relation to the augmented, modified or synthetic body, i.e., the augmented human, the manufacturer of the augmentation, body part or device; the supplier of the augmentation, body part or device (e.g., a hospital). There is some guidance from the Department of Health (1983)¹⁷⁹ which provides a position on this subject (affirmed by the MHRA):

On implantation, an implant becomes the property of the person in whom it has been implanted and it remains his or her property even if it is subsequently removed. Following the patient's death, it forms part of his or her estate unless there is any specific provision to the contrary.

This position is, however, disputed.¹⁸⁰ Quigley and Ayihongbe also question both its legal provenance and usefulness, noting further that “the specific question of the property status of medical devices once implanted into or integrated with the body has not been tested in the courts”.¹⁸¹

¹⁷⁴ Barfield, Woodrow, and Alexander Williams, "Law, Cyborgs, and Technologically Enhanced Brains", *Philosophies* 2.1, 2017, p.6.

¹⁷⁵ From a consumer law perspective, such elements could be considered defective products though.

¹⁷⁶ Barfield and Williams, op. cit., 2017.

¹⁷⁷ [2006] EWCA Crim 1502

¹⁷⁸ [2002] 1 Cr.App.R. 519

¹⁷⁹ Department of Health & Social Security, Health Notice HN(83)6, Health service management ownership of implants and removal of cardiac pacemakers after death, 1983.

¹⁸⁰ Arguing that “there is no logical contractual way that ownership can pass merely because an item remains in a person's possession”. See Fifield, Kerry, “Ownership of medical implants”, Clarke Wilmott, 2012. <https://www.clarkewillmott.com/blog/ownership-of-medical-implants/>

¹⁸¹ Quigley and Ayihongbe, op. cit., 2018, p.288.

5. Discussion

Summary of issues

Our literature review has identified several legal issues related to HETs in the UK (from various perspectives. These include:

- Changing of human capacities and, consequently, legal responsibilities
- Human rights considerations related to informed consent (and the conditions of consent), personal autonomy, privacy¹⁸², bodily integrity, reproductive rights
- Legal obligations to take cognitive enhancing drugs
- Liabilities for failures to enhance
- Security, safety and product liability
- Intellectual property rights.

Challenges

Quigley and Ayihongbe¹⁸³ highlight one challenge - this is the creation by the law of “artificial constructs that become the object of regulatory attention of dedicated regulators who operate within legally defined spheres of influence or “silos”¹⁸⁴. Quigley and Ayihongbe underline “the law takes a ‘bounded object’ approach, constructing medical devices as different types of objects: ‘risk objects’, ‘marketised objects’, ‘innovation objects’, and so on” which “consequence of this and other regulatory framings is that, to the extent that persons factor into the regulation and governance regarding medical devices, they do so in relation to these particular object-focused frames of reference.”¹⁸⁵ This, they see as problematic given, as they further explain, that “the transgression of the bodily boundary and the re-formation of persons as *integrated persons* means that neither the object nor the subject ought to be construed as fixed”.¹⁸⁶

In relation to cognitive enhancement devices, Maslen et al suggest “there are many other regulatory challenges that remain unaddressed. In particular, the challenge of promoting safe use is not to be underestimated”.¹⁸⁷

¹⁸² Note, “Medical devices can be interpreted to include medical informatics which are impacted by the EU GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation).” British Medical Association, “Brexit Briefing Medicines and medical devices regulation Maintaining an effective working relationship between the UK and the EU”, 2017. <https://www.bma.org.uk/-/media/files/pdfs/collective%20voice/influence/europe/bma-brexit-briefing-medicines-and-medical-devices-regulation.pdf?la=en>

¹⁸³ Quigley, Muireann, and Semande Ayihongbe, “Everyday Cyborgs: On Integrated Persons and Integrated Goods”, *Medical Law Review*, Vol. 26, Iss. 2, 2018, pp. 276-30.

¹⁸⁴ Citing Laurie, Graeme, “Liminality and the Limits of Law in Health Research Regulation: What are we Missing in the Spaces in-Between?”, *Medical Law Review*, Volume 25, Issue 1, 2017, pp. 47–72.

¹⁸⁵ Quigley and Ayihongbe, op. cit., 2018.

¹⁸⁶ Quigley and Ayihongbe, op. cit., 2018.

¹⁸⁷ Maslen, Hannah, et al. “The regulation of cognitive enhancement devices: refining Maslen et al.'s model”, *Journal of Law and the Biosciences*, 2, 3, 2015, pp. 754-767

Another challenge relates to the destabilisation of the human body and the concept of bodily integrity – this is a global challenge. Wicks states in *The State and the Body: Legal Regulation of Bodily Autonomy*: “Our bodies are central to the landmark events in our lives: being born, growing up, making love, having children, falling ill and dying. They are also, increasingly, changeable.”¹⁸⁸

Gaps

Some commentators have explicitly highlighted the “continued existence of a regulatory gap”.¹⁸⁹ Some other specific gaps relate to:

- Legal discussion on reversibility or irreversibility of human enhancement and its consequences.
- How the current and future interests of individuals might be balanced in terms of their enhancement choices and decisions.
- Devotion of “relatively little attention” in courts to the concept of bodily integrity¹⁹⁰ and preparedness of the courts to deal with the challenges raised by the “the linking of the organic, biological person with synthetic, inorganic parts and devices”.¹⁹¹
- How the law might address and deal with the replacement of a healthy body part for a prosthetic one. We found no explicit statement of law or academic discourse that shows this is prohibited. Though, if such replacement was contrary to the provisions of law, it would be illegal, e.g., is an assault offence, or is carried out in prohibited circumstances (e.g., on an underage person without valid consent) and causes of legal action might arise in cases of clinical or medical negligence.

6. Conclusions

This report provided a brief discussion of legal developments related to human enhancement in the UK and an analysis of national legal scholarship. It also addressed specific legal questions, and briefly presented some challenges and gaps, as evident from the analysis.

The report on *Human enhancement and the future of work* (from a joint workshop hosted by the Academy of Medical Sciences, the British Academy, the Royal Academy of Engineering and the Royal Society)¹⁹² underlined that “To maximise any benefit from enhancement technologies, we must understand the complexities of these context-specific outcomes and involve individuals in the design and integration of technologies, and in the design of any regulatory frameworks”.¹⁹³ Further the report highlighted another key aspect of work-related enhancement in particular – how different regulatory regimes apply to various HETs (e.g., digital versus drugs or invasive versus non-invasive) and how the levels of regulatory oversight vary. In some cases, self-regulation be appropriate. The report also

¹⁸⁸ Wicks, Elizabeth, *The State and the Body: Legal Regulation of Bodily Autonomy*, Hart Publishing, 2016, p.1.

¹⁸⁹ Maslen et al, op. cit., 2015; Maslen et al, op. cit., 2014

¹⁹⁰ Herring, Jonathan, and Jesse Wall, “The Nature and Significance of the Right to Bodily Integrity”, *The Cambridge Law Journal*, Vol. 76, Iss. 3, 2017, pp. 566-588 [p. 569]

¹⁹¹ Quigley and Ayihongbe, op. cit., 2018.

¹⁹² November 2012. <https://acmedsci.ac.uk/viewFile/publicationDownloads/135228646747.pdf>

¹⁹³ Ibid.

suggests there might be circumstances where enhancements should be encouraged or even mandatory, particularly where work involves responsibility for the safety of others (e.g., bus drivers or airline pilots).¹⁹⁴ The report also calls to attention two other important dimensions. One is that “continuous monitoring to inform the re-assessment of any policy or regulatory decisions is vital”, and another is that “the international aspects of enhancement are inescapable”.¹⁹⁵ In moving forward in regulating the human enhancement aspects in the UK, these points along with the gaps and challenges identified in this report should be noted.

In line with the SIENNA legal workshop recommendations, we would also like to underline that any legal discussions and responses to developments in HETs in the UK should adequately consider the consequences the different types of technologies, the severity and nature (reversibility or irreversibility) of their application in particular contexts – especially with respect to access, equality and changes to human (bodily) autonomy and choice.

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¹⁹⁵ Ibid.

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